

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Comparison of search trends between fluoride toothpaste and whitening toothpaste in the Philippines: A descriptive study

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ABSTRACT

Background: Google Trends (GT) can be used to investigate the search trend of oral health improvement-seeking behavior by providing analyzed data of search queries in Google search. This study aims to compare the search trends for fluoride toothpaste and whitening toothpaste among Filipinos from 2004 until 2022. **Methods:** Using GT, search parameters using the keywords “fluoride toothpaste” and “whitening toothpaste”, the Philippines as country, 2004 to 2022 for time range, health as category, and web search as database. **Results:** Based on the data provided by GT, the highest peak for interest in fluoride toothpaste was 100% in August 2004. However, the search for whitening toothpaste began to surpass the search for fluoride toothpaste from September 2010 until the present. **Discussion:** The search for whitening toothpaste is relatively high compared to fluoride toothpaste from 2004-2022 in the Philippines. **Conclusions:** Filipinos were more interested in searching for whitening toothpaste than fluoride toothpaste.

Keywords health behavior, internet behavior, teeth whitening, toothpastes

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1 | Introduction

Among the many goals of dental treatment is to restore and improve the teeth in the most natural and aesthetic way that meets the patient’s needs and demands. The possibilities

of achieving these have significantly improved over the years with the emergence of new treatment methods, advancements of technology, and the discovery of new dental materials and techniques.¹

One of the many the most noteworthy advancement over the past decade is the development of

Figure 1. Interest over time of the searches for whitening toothpaste versus fluoride toothpaste from year 2004-2022 of Filipino people

tooth whitening and advanced restorative as well as prosthetic materials and techniques.¹ There are various types of toothpastes marketed globally, and some manufacturers change the variety of formulations to produce products that cater consumers on their specific needs. Some toothpaste products claim that it is for caries prevention, tooth whitening, sensitivity prevention, gum health and total oral health.² There is a substantial number of toothpastes available as tooth whitening products which appear to contain materials that may remove extrinsic tooth stains.³

Data gathered from the internet, such as search cycles, are being integrated into health informatics research and have become advantageous tool for exploring human behavior. Google Trends, a tool that provides information on trends and the varied online interests among people over time, has been the most popular tool for examining online behavior.⁴

The primary aim of this study is to evaluate the Filipinos' interest towards whitening toothpaste and fluoride toothpaste from 2004-2022.

2 | Results

2.1. Interest over time

Filipinos searched highest for whitening toothpaste in August 2004 at 100% while the search for fluoride toothpaste was highest in November 2005 at 60% only.

The search for both whitening and fluoride toothpaste in July 2018 was equal at 1%. The interest of Filipino people in both search terms was non-existent in July and October 2014, and December and January 2013. The search for whitening toothpaste was constantly higher than the search for fluoride toothpaste from September 2010 until the present. (Figure 1).

● fluoride toothpaste ● whitening toothpaste

Figure 2. Compared breakdown by subregions of the searches whitening toothpaste and fluoride toothpaste

2.2 Compared breakdown by subregion.

In terms of the highest searches for whitening toothpaste, the first ranked subregion is Central Visayas (100%), followed by Metro Manila (60%), Calabarzon (59%), and Central Luzon (58%). For the interest in fluoride toothpaste, the first ranked subregion is Central Luzon (42%), followed by Calabarzon (41%), Metro Manila (40%) and Central Visayas (0%) (Figure 2).

3 | Discussion

This study describes the comparison of search trends between whitening toothpaste and fluoride toothpaste by Filipino people. Majority of the Filipinos have more interest on whitening toothpaste. Filipinos searched highest for whitening toothpaste in August 2004 at 100% while the search for fluoride toothpaste was highest in November 2005 at 60% only. The search for

whitening toothpaste was constantly higher than the search for fluoride toothpaste from September 2010 until present.

Overall, the results show that Filipinos has grown a greater interest in whitening toothpaste than typical fluoride toothpaste. From September 2010 until present, the search cycles for whitening toothpaste have remained significantly higher. This may be an indication of the Filipinos' grown inclination towards achieving aesthetically pleasing teeth and thereby improving one's self-confidence.

Physical appearance has a big influence that affects the quality of individual social interaction, especially in terms of non-verbal interactions. Tooth color is one of the things that affect physical appearance. Various efforts to improve the aesthetics of tooth color should be studied further, including the use of whitening toothpaste.⁵

In addition to preventing tooth decay and periodontal disease, oral care products that focus on whitening teeth are increasing. This is for cosmetic reasons as many people prefer white teeth and a bright smile, as this can also affect their quality of life.⁶

Perceptions about the appearance of teeth form a component of body image. Similar to body image development, dental

aesthetic trends are influenced by ideals, which are determined by a variety of sociocultural and personal factors. These ideals are disseminated through socialization agents in which the mass media play an important role. Every day, the media is flooded with advertisements and messages that capitalize on public concerns about body.⁷

Based on current and previous research, it appears that poor dental appearance can cause others to judge negatively in various personality categories. This might have a great impact to social interactions, friendships and romantic relationships or career opportunities. It is likely that more and more dental patients will desire teeth whitening than other cosmetic procedures.⁸

However, this study is an explorative process to understand the perceptions and behaviors of Filipino people towards whitening and fluoride toothpaste.

4 | Methods

In this study, STROBE reporting guideline was used to facilitate proper discussion of the result.

4.1. Data acquisition

The Google Trends website was accessed August 18, 2022. The terms “fluoride toothpaste” and “whitening toothpaste” were used. The parameters that were chosen were

Philippines as country, 2004 to 2022 for time range, health as category, and web search as database.

4.2. Statistical analysis

Descriptive analysis was done from the graphic user interface of Google Trends. Data were expressed in percentages.

5 | Conclusions

Due to Cosmetology trends, majority of the Filipinos are into whitening toothpastes. Whitening toothpaste caught more attention of the consumers because people are getting more self-conscious on how they look, especially when they smile. In cosmetics, whitening products dominate the market. This is also true in Cosmetic Dentistry; more consumers seek for products that would aid them or take them a step closer for a bright and beautiful smile. This notion causes more greater interest for whitening toothpaste than ordinary fluoride toothpaste, people on the internet tend to research about whitening toothpaste and its whereabouts more than fluoride toothpaste. Search trend results from Google Trends from 2004-2022 in the Philippines also verifies the growing interests among Filipinos towards whitening toothpaste.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, E.T., W.E.; Original Draft Preparation, E.T., W.E.;

Validation, E.T.; Title, E.T.; Abstract, W.E.; Editing, E.T., W.E., M.J., M.B., D.M.; Introduction, E.T., W.E.; Results, M.J.; Discussion, M.J.; Methods, D.M.; Conclusions, M.B.; Citations, E.T., W.E., M.J.

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Institutional Review Board Statement

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and approved by the Ethics

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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